

24 **1. Introduction**

25 EG has been applied as a refrigerant in many fields like automobiles [1]. For automotive applications, the
26 cooling agent has been used to transfer heat to prevent car engine malfunction. In an automobile's cooling
27 system, a 1:1 dilution of mixture between EG and water is commonly used. However, the -OH group in EG is
28 not stable, which will oxidize or degrade to become different acid types. Therefore, the formed acids in the EG
29 solution will cause corrosion problems and reduce the machine's lifetime as time goes on. Corrosion inhibitors
30 are usually added to the coolant solution to prevent acid formation. However, the coolant solution still needs to
31 be frequently changed because it can become more acidic over time and lose its rust-inhibiting properties,
32 causing corrosion on automobile radiators. To reduce the number of changing coolant solutions and protect metal
33 surfaces in the cooling system of automobile radiators, superhydrophobic anti-corrosion metal surfaces can be a
34 good option.

35 Recently, researches on SHS have become one of the hottest topics due to potential applications for self-
36 cleaning [2]; oil-water separation [3], and anti-corrosion [4]. To our knowledge, there is no work studying the
37 corrosion performance of such surfaces in coolant solutions. Among the methods to get SHS, the femtosecond
38 laser ablation has attracted many researchers' interest for its high efficiency, simple process, and lower cost [5,6]
39 and is widely used in producing the superhydrophobic anti-corrosion surface [7].

40 This paper uses three methods to produce superhydrophobic anti-corrosion aluminum surfaces by
41 femtosecond laser ablation and chemical coatings. All the samples show excellent superhydrophobicity and anti-
42 corrosion properties with EG solution. Moreover, we made comparisons of the samples prepared by the three
43 methods to suggest the most suitable one for the production of surfaces working in engine coolant environments
44 which brings a possibility to apply EG repellent metal surfaces in the cooling system of automobile radiators for
45 more prolonged usage, resulting in cost-saving and sustainability development.

46

47 2. Experimental

48 2.1. Material

49 PDMS (Sylgard®184, Dow Corning CO., Michigan), 99.999% pure Al substrate (Zhong Nuo Advanced
50 Material Technology Co., Ltd), TTFOS (Shanghai yuanye Bio-Technology Co., Ltd), and fumed silica
51 (Hydrophobic-260, 7-40nm, Aladdin biochemical technology co. LTD) were used in this research.

52 2.2. Fabrication

53 A Al plate (10 x 10 cm²) was divided into smaller pieces with different dimensions (1.5 x 1.5 cm², 2 x 2 cm²).
54 Then, these pieces were ultrasonically cleaned with deionized water (DI water) and ethanol for 15 minutes,
55 respectively, to remove the impurities.

56 Micro-nano structures on the substrate were fabricated by a femtosecond laser (Fig. 1a). The distance between
57 the ablating lines was 100 μm, and the scanning speed was 1 mm*s⁻¹. The fabricated structure is a grid pattern.

58 The three methods are described below (Fig. 1b):

- 59 • Method 1 (M1): Al was fabricated by 200 mW of femtosecond laser power. Then, the PDMS and curing
60 agent (weight ratio of 10:1) were dissolved in the toluene (5 wt.%). Then, we coated the solution on the
61 surface and heated the sample for 1 hour at 150 °C.
- 62 • Method 2 (M2): The PDMS and curing agent were mixed (weight ratio of 10:1) and then coated on Al
63 substrate. Then, the sample was put on the table for 10 minutes and then heated for 1 hour at 150 °C,
64 followed by a femtosecond laser ablation (35 mW).
- 65 • Method 3 (M3): A femtosecond laser (200 mW) produces micro-nano structures on the Al. Then, we
66 prepared the synthesized solution, which referred to Jia Hu. et group [8]. The preparation process was as
67 follows: at room temperature, 0.1 g TTFOS was added to 9.9 g ethanol and stirred for 2 hours to make the
68 TTFOS dissolve utterly, then 0.02 g SiO₂ was added, and after 2 hours of stirring, 1 g PDMS was added and
69 stirred for 1 hour. Finally, a 0.1 g curing agent was added and stirred for 15 minutes to make the solution

70 thoroughly mixed. After coating this solution, the sample was heated for 5 minutes at 160 °C.

71 2.3. Characterization

72 The surface morphology and the element composition were characterized by a scanning electron microscope
73 (SEM) (ProX800-07334, Phenom World), an energy dispersive spectrometer (EDS). The samples' wettabilities
74 were tested by a contact angle measurement machine (powereach JC2000D3). The anti-corrosion properties were
75 tested by the electrochemistry method (EC-Lab, VMP 3) with a 50 vol.% EG solution. After the corrosion test,
76 the sample was dried and then retested by the 3D confocal microscope (KEYENCE VK-X 1000) to see the
77 surface morphology change.

78
79 Fig. 1. (a) femtosecond laser system; (b) the chemical coatings on the substrates; (c-h) surface morphologies and
80 element compositions of the samples.

81

82 3. Result and Discussion

83 Fig. 1c-h shows morphologies of the surfaces before and after superhydrophobic modifications. In M1 and M3,
84 significant microgrid patterns did not change much after chemical modification. However, when zooming in on
85 structures at higher magnifications, they were smoother with more nanoparticles' appearance and the
86 disappearance of micro-nano cavities. (Fig. 1e,f,h). The surfaces in M2 contained cube shapes with cracks on
87 the top, significantly differing from the samples prepared by M1 and M3 (Fig. 1g). Moreover, Si and F

88 appearances indicated chemically modified coatings on the samples of these three methods.

89 In Fig. 2a, all the fabricated samples showed excellent liquid repellency with the contact angles (CAs) greater
90 than 150° and sliding angles (SAs) smaller than 10° (Table S1 and Fig. S1). Without the micro-nano structure,
91 flat surfaces only with the chemical treatment cannot become superhydrophobic (Fig. 2b). After laser ablation,
92 the contact area between the droplet and the substrate had an about 10-fold decrease (Table S2), which played an
93 important role in improving hydrophobicity. According to the Cassie-Baxter model [9,10], the air layer formed
94 on the surface prevented the droplet from penetrating the structure (Fig. S2). Also, the hydrophobic molecules
95 attached to the surface formed a protective layer in M1 and M3, reducing the surface energy and enhancing
96 hydrophobicity. The laser processing part was mainly cured PDMS layer in M2, while the Al substrate was not
97 exposed, and the PDMS coating was in effect. PDMS had low surface energy, and the rough structure enhanced
98 the sample hydrophobicity.

99 Fig. 2. (a) water and EG CAs and SAs; (b) representative CAs of the flat Al modified by three methods; (c)
100 various liquids' wetting states on different samples.
101

102 When dropping the EG solution, the liquid stuck on the flat Al immediately and could not stream on the
103 surface (Video S1). Conversely, the droplets would bounce off the SHS (Videos S2-S4). Furthermore, all the
104 droplets on the flat Al spread out on the surface (Fig. 2c1). The CuCl_2 drop's color changed from blue to black
105 because of the precipitation of Cu produced by the reaction with the Al. In Fig. 2c2-c4, all the liquids could stay
106 a droplet state and not react to the SHSs.

107

108 Fig. 3. Corrosion results. (a) Tafel curve of flat Al and samples by three methods modification; (b-e) surface

109 morphologies before and after the corrosion tests; red arrows showed the surfaces' damages; (f) chemical

110 reaction on the flat surface and SHS.

111 The corrosion rate (CR) and the corrosion inhibition efficiency (CIE) was calculated by the values from the

112 Tafel curve with equation (1) and (2) (Fig. 3a). After calculation, the CR dropped by three orders of magnitude,

113 and the CIE dropped more than 91% after chemical modification (Table S3). In Fig. 3b-e, the flat sample showed

114 apparent damage after the corrosion test, but the SHS made by M1 and M3 showed no damage. The surface

115 fabricated by M2 showed some damage because of the worse connection between the PDMS layer and the Al

116 surface after laser treatment. The primary corrosion process of the EG solution is electrochemical corrosion.

117 When the corrosion happens, it will create bubbles on the metal, called cavitation. The cavitation gradually

118 corrodes the metal surface, making irregular holes on the surface and accelerating the metal corrosion. The side

119 effect of EG corrosion is acid corrosion. Over time, EG will decompose or oxidize into different acids. Due to

120 the characterization, all the results showed that the superhydrophobicity positively influences the corrosion

121 results because of the air layer formed by the micro-nano structure and chemical layer protection (Fig. 3f).

$$122 \quad R(\text{mm}/\text{year}) = \frac{3.27 \times 10^{-3} \times I_{\text{corr}} \times M}{nd} \quad (1)$$

123 Where M is related to the metal's atomic mass ($\text{g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$), d means the metal density ($\text{g} \cdot \text{cm}^{-3}$), and n denotes

124 the number of electrons related to the oxidizing of an atom of the element in the corrosion process.

$$125 \quad \text{CIE}(\%) = \frac{I_{\text{corr}} - I'_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

126 Where the I_{corr} and I_{corr}' are corrosion current density before and after.

127

128 **4. Conclusion**

129 We used three methods to get superhydrophobic Al surfaces, and all the samples showed EG CAs of more
130 than 150° with SAs smaller than 10° . The mechanism for surface wettability change is explained by
131 combinations between micro-nano structure formations and low surface energy. Additionally, the corrosion
132 properties in 50 vol.% EG solution have better improvements when the samples become superhydrophobic. The
133 CR and CIE, with noticeable drops, demonstrate their improvements. Based on the anti-corrosion performances
134 and the sample preparations, method 1 is suggested for applying in a corrosive EG environment of a cooling
135 system.

136

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143

144 Appendix A.

145 Supplementary data is put on the supplementary files.

146

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